

Kim, J., & Oki, T. (2011). Visioneering: An essential framework in sustainability science. *Sustainability Science*, 6(2), 247–251. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-011-0130-8>

Wiek, A., & Iwaniec, D. (2014). Quality criteria for visions and visioning in sustainability science. *Sustainability Science*, 9(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-013-0208-6>

Colloff, M. J., Martín-López, B., Lavorel, S., Locatelli, B., Gorddard, R., Longaretti, P.-Y., Walters, G., Van Kerkhoff, L., Wyborn, C., Coreau, A., Wise, R. M., Dunlop, M., Degeorges, P., Grantham, H., Overton, I. C., Williams, R. D., Doherty, M. D., Capon, T., Sanderson, T., & Murphy, H. T. (2017). An integrative research framework for enabling transformative adaptation. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 68, 87–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2016.11.007>

Wyborn, C., Montana, J., Kalas, N., Davila, F., Clement, S., S Izquierdo Tort, Knowles, N., Louder, E., Madhurya Balan, J Chambers, L Christel, Zemp, A. D., Forsyth, T., Henderson, G., M Lim, M J Martinez Harms, Merçon, J., Nuesiri, E., L Pereira, ... Wood, S. (2020). Research and action agenda for sustaining diverse and just futures for life on Earth. *Biodiversity Revisited*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12086.52804/2>

Pereira, L., Davies, K. K., Belder, E., Ferrier, S., Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen, S., Kim, H., Kuiper, J. J., Okayasu, S., Palomo, M. G., Pereira, H. M., Peterson, G., Sathyapalan, J., Schoolenberg, M., Alkemade, R., Carvalho Ribeiro, S., Greenaway, A., Hauck, J., King, N., Lazarova, T., ... Lundquist, C. J. (2020). Developing multiscale and integrative nature–people scenarios using the Nature Futures Framework. *People and Nature*, 2(4), 1172–1195. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10146>

Pereira, L., Kuiper, J. J., Selomane, O., Aguiar, A. P. D., Asrar, G. R., Bennett, E. M., Biggs, R., Calvin, K., Hedden, S., Hsu, A., Jabbour, J., King, N., Köberle, A. C., Lucas, P., Nel, J., Norström, A. V., Peterson, G., Sitas, N., Trisos, C., ... Ward, J. (2021). Advancing a toolkit of diverse futures approaches for global environmental assessments. *Ecosystems and People*, 17(1), 191–204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2021.1901783>